

Design Optimization of Fuzzy-PID Controller for Autonomous Hovercraft Path Tracking

(Rekabentuk Optimasi Pengawal Fuzzy-PID untuk Penjejakan Laluan Hoverkraf Berautonomi)

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ABSTRACT

Hovercraft is a very active and agile vehicle where it needs an optimum and stable control. Autonomous hovercraft control based on Advanced Process Control is not widely introduced. In this paper, a design of fuzzy-PID control will be introduced. Fuzzy-PID control combines PID controller and fuzzy controller which has two inputs and three outputs. The fuzzy controller will tune the PID controller parameters when the system response shows error and error rate. The autonomous hovercraft model is described and implemented using the Euler Lagrange approach. Fuzzy-PID based controller and conventional PID controller are compared by simulation. The path tracking of autonomous hovercraft was tested using MATLAB Simulink software. Path tracking is important for achieving a global stabilization and exponential convergence of a tracking error with desired trajectory. In this paper, simulation results show the trajectory position of autonomous hovercraft in both surge and sway position and also path tracking in a circle. The simulation results show that fuzzy-PID controller has a better performance compared to the classical PID controller. This concludes that the proposed controller shows the effectiveness and good resilience where it has advantages of rapid respond, high stability and tracking accuracy and also good in anti-interference. The fuzzy-PID controller is proven to be an appropriate choice for path tracking control of an autonomous hovercraft.

Keywords: Path tracking; Hovercraft; Trajectory tracking; Fuzzy PID Control; Simulation in Simulink

ABSTRAK

Hoverkraf merupakan kenderaan yang sangat aktif dan tangkas dimana ia memerlukan kawalan yang optimum dan stabil. Kawalan hoverkraf berautonomi berasaskan kawalan proses termaju tidak banyak diperkenalkan. Di dalam kertas kajian ini, rekabentuk kawalan fuzzy-PID untuk penjejakan laluan sebuah hoverkraf berautonomi akan diperkenalkan. Penjejakan laluan adalah penting untuk memperoleh kestabilan global dan penumpuan eksponensial posisi ralat penjejakan dengan landar ruang diingini. Pengawal fuzzy-PID adalah gabungan pengawal PID dan pengawal fuzzy yang mempunyai dua masukan dan tiga keluaran. Pengawal fuzzy akan menala parameter pengawal PID apabila respons sistem menunjukkan ralat dan kadar ralat. Model hoverkraf berautonomi berdasarkan pendekatan Euler Lagrange diperkenalkan dan digunakan. Kawalan berdasarkan fuzzy-PID dan konvensional PID dibandingkan melalui simulasi. Penjejakan laluan hoverkraf berautonomi ini diuji menggunakan perisian MATLAB/Simulink. Di dalam kertas ini, simulasi menunjukkan hasil posisi landar ruang hoverkraf dalam keadaan pusuan dan huyung serta penjejakan laluan dalam bentuk bulatan. Hasil simulasi menunjukkan pengawal fuzzy-PID memberikan prestasi yang lebih baik berbanding pengawal konvensional PID dimana dapat membuktikan model kawalan sasaran ini memberikan keberkesanan dan ketahanan yang baik. Ia mempunyai kelebihan tindak balas dengan pantas, kestabilan yang tinggi, ketepatan pengesanan dan menghapuskan gangguan dengan baik. Jadi, pengawal fuzzy-PID ternyata sesuai untuk penjejakan laluan untuk hoverkraf berautonomi.

Kata Kunci: Penjejakan laluan; Hoverkraf; Penjejakan landar ruang; Pengawal Fuzzy-PID; Simulasi di Simulink

INTRODUCTION

Hovercraft is a hybrid vehicle that can operate in various kinds of surface such as land, water, mud, and many more. Nowadays, hovercraft has become a vehicle with numerous functions. According to (Liu et al. 2016) and (Fu et al. 2018), hovercraft is used for water pollution monitoring, coast guard, and military operations. With the rapidly evolving technology, hovercrafts become more complex with the inclusion of electronics components, sensors, drivers, controller design. The example of 3D model of an autonomous hovercraft is as shown in Figure 1. However, the most crucial criteria in developing and designing an autonomous robot especially hovercraft is the control. This is because the ability and optimization of an autonomous robot depends on its controller. The most important concern of this hovercraft control is its stability and tracking control.

FIGURE 1. 3D model of an autonomous hovercraft

FIGURE 2. Configuration model of hovercraft

According to (Tran, Son, et al. 2020) and (Hussein 2013), there are three types of rotors in a hovercraft as shown in Figure 2. The first is an inclined servo motor, a rotor duct fan mounted on the y-axis and a propeller mounted on the z-axis of the vehicle. From (Lu et al. 2019) and (Fu, Wang, et al. 2017), path control is important and practical issue in autonomous robots and divided into two categories which are trajectory tracking and path tracking control. In trajectory tracking control, a graph based on a time relationship is used to achieve the desired trajectory of an autonomous hovercraft. Meanwhile, path tracking control, the desired trajectory of a hovercraft is based on the geometrical parameters that are easily achieved.

Trajectory tracking control is important for hovercraft to arrive at a certain location at a certain time while path tracking control is needed for hovercraft to trace or track the desired trail given by geometrical parameters at a certain speed.

PID control is a conventional control that is often used especially on autonomous robot controls. According to (Guney & Demir 2017), tracking control and stability can be achieved by using PID control. Typically, PID-based autonomous robots use the steering drive angle error as input and the steering angle of the robot as the output. Although PID control can achieve stability and control tracking, the accuracy of the system is still poor. Therefore, fuzzy logic control is introduced to achieve optimal control as fuzzy control capability can control objects with complex mathematical models and nonlinear. However, fuzzy control also has some shortcomings where it is challenging to eliminate steady-state error low steady control accuracy and not smooth enough. Therefore, the basic fuzzy control will be combined with the conventional PID control to overcome each other's shortcomings and ultimately provides more optimal control that meets the specified requirements.

FIGURE 3. Fuzzy control structure

In this paper, a fuzzy-PID control design for hovercraft path tracking will be proposed. According to (Tiep et al. 2018), the fuzzy-PID control that is based on fuzzy controller and PID controller will have two inputs and three outputs as illustrated in Figure 3. According to (Chen et al. 2018) and (Phu & Choi 2019), the fuzzy controller will tune the PID controller parameters, K_d , K_i and K_p when error and error rate exists. The kinematic and dynamic equations of the autonomous hovercraft is described using the Euler Lagrange approach. Expected results will show how the proposed controller can facilitate tuning for PID control, improve the path tracking control and compare PID and fuzzy-PID control optimization. The results expect the fuzzy-PID controller to have better performance than the conventional PID controller as it has advantages of fast response, high stability and tracking accuracy which makes the fuzzy-PID control suitable for route tracking control of a hovercraft.

METHODOLOGY

Experiment Design and Procedure

The research process is illustrated as the flowchart shown in Figure 4. The process of conducting the problem statement, literature review, identifying the hovercraft equations is made earlier before proceeding with the simulation process.

FIGURE 4. Project flowchart

The block diagram for the overall autonomous hovercraft tracking control is as shown in Figure 5, where there is reference tracking, PID and fuzzy-PID controllers, and a hovercraft model. The path tracking reference provides the desired route for the hovercraft to track. Paths can consist of straight lines, circles, and ellipses.

FIGURE 5. Block diagram

This path tracking reference produces parameters x_d and y_d which are the desired surge and sway positions respectively. This reference position will be the input to the PID or fuzzy-PID controller to be processed. The process carried out in calculating the desired value of velocity and

angular velocity which in turn becomes the input to the hovercraft model. Hovercraft models constructed from dynamic and kinematic equations as well as interference are introduced. In this block, the velocity values and the reference angle velocity will be used to produce the hovercraft's oscillation, sway and angle positions and these values form the basis for the hovercraft to move. The hovercraft's actual surge, sway and angle positions will be fed back to the control block to reduce errors.

Hovercraft Model and Parameters

The small -scale autonomous hovercraft in this study paper was published using the Euler Lagrange method according to (Fu, Gao, et al. 2017), and (Tran, Lam, et al. 2020). Based on Figure 6, the equation of motion of hovercraft can be expressed as Equation 1 to Equation 3 which is also the hovercraft's kinematic equations.

FIGURE 6. Hovercraft model

$$\dot{x} = u \cos \psi - v \sin \psi \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{y} = v \cos \psi + u \sin \psi \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{\psi} = r \quad (3)$$

Where u is the surge velocities, v is the sway velocities and r is the yaw angle velocities. The dynamical model of the hovercraft can be simplified using Equation 4 until Equation 6.

$$\dot{u} = vr + \frac{\tau_u}{m} \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{v} = -ur \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{r} = \tau_r \quad (6)$$

Where m is the mass, τ_u is the torque in surge and τ_r is the torque in sway. For this hovercraft, the parameters to be used for the equation are as shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1 Hovercraft's Parameters

Parameters	Symbol	Value
Mass	M	2.1kg
Angle	$\Psi(t)$	30°
Moment of Inertia	I	0.000257kgm ²

Control System Design

For the tracking model, the input to this system is a real-time moving point where the hovercraft can follow the track by following this point. This tracking target is set to a circle with a size specified to a radius of value one. The approach used to construct the circle model for this path tracking is the circle parametric equation whose basis is as in Equation 5

$$x = r \cos t \tag{7}$$

$$y = r \sin t \tag{8}$$

Based on Figure 7, there are two gains on the tracking model. By changing their values, the shape of the tracking will change such as ellipses and circles can be set. In a tracking target, the hovercraft will keep a distance with a moving point to be set at 0.01 inches on the system.

FIGURE 7. Simulink model of path tracking

For fuzzy control, Mamdani fuzzy type will be used where there are two inputs namely error (e) and change in error (ce). This fuzzy controller will tune the parameters on the PID controller namely Kp, Ki and Kd. The self-tuning of the PID controller will find fuzzy relationships with all three components of the PID controller. For the fuzzy-PID control, to determine the error variable and the error change, five fuzzy membership function inputs were used namely negative big (NB), negative small (NS), zero (Z), positive small (PS) and positive big (PB). The output for this

controller is selected from four values, namely very big (VB), large (B), medium (M) and small (S).

During the operation of the control system, if it continuously detects errors and error rates, tuning the PID parameters in real-time by following the rules of the fuzzy controller, will make the system achieve good dynamic and azimuth performance. By using a PID controller, the velocity and angular velocity of the hovercraft can be controlled. There are some fuzzy rules for determining error variables and error changes and these can be scheduled as per Table .2. In this paper, the membership function format used is if the error is negative big (NB), and the error rate is also negative big (NB), so Kp is very big (VB), Ki is small (S) and Kd is also small (S).

Simulations for the PID controller and the fuzzy-PID controller were performed separately due to the different controller models. According to (Somwanshi et al. 2019), the basics for both controllers are more or less the same. For the PID controller, the hovercraft's position and angle deviation which is the feedback from the hovercraft model becomes the input of this controller. The output of the PID controller will control the velocity and angular velocity of the hovercraft. Whereas, for fuzzy-PID based control systems, a fuzzy controller is added in front of the PID controller. The inputs to this fuzzy controller are position, azimuth error and error rate while the output of this controller results from of the parameter values Kp, Ki and also Kd on real -time tuning. Once the parameters are tuned, the PID controller will begin to control the velocity and angular velocity of the hovercraft.

The hovercraft model is constructed based on the published hovercraft dynamic and kinematic equations. The kinematics equations are as Equation 1 until Equation 3 whereas the dynamic equations are as Equation 4 until Equation 6.

All these equations are combined in the form of blocks to obtain a simulation model in MATLAB Simulink software. Interference such as inertia and friction based on (Cabecinhas et al. 2018) are also included to make the hovercraft model more realistic. The position and angle deviation of the hovercraft will be fed back to the input of the PID or fuzzy-PID controller and the output of this controller will control the velocity and angular velocity of the hovercraft. The hovercraft model built on MATLAB Simulink is as shown in Figure 8

FIGURE 8. Simulink model of an autonomous hovercraft

For the tracking error curve, according to (Xu et al. 2014) Equation 6 which is the speed diversion is used.

$$e = \sqrt{(\dot{x} - \dot{x}')^2 + (\dot{y} - \dot{y}')^2} - d \quad (9)$$

Where x' and y' are the coordinates of the moving point in the tracking. The diversion i.e. the hovercraft azimuth error is as in Equation 7

$$\dot{\theta} = \tan^{-1} \frac{\dot{y} - \dot{y}'}{\dot{x} - \dot{x}'} \quad (10)$$

TABLE 2. Fuzzy Rule Table for Kp/Ki/Kd gain

e/ce	NB	NM	Z	PS	PB
NB	VB/S/S	VB/M/S	S/M/VB	S/M/B	M/S/S
NS	VB/B/S	B/B/S	S/B/B	S/B/B	B/S/S
Z	B/B/S	M/B/M	S/VB/B	S/VB/M	VB/VB/S
PS	M/B/M	S/B/B	S/B/B	M/B/S	VB/B/S
PB	S/S/M	S/S/VB	S/M/VB	B/M/S	VB/S/S

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Controllability Test

Controllability tests should be performed to test whether the system equations can be controlled or not. If the output is $unco = 0$, the system equation can be controlled. The results of the controllability test are shown in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9. Controllability test result

After being tested, the equation of this hovercraft system proved to be controllable because it managed to obtain the result of $unco = 0$

Trajectory Tracking of Surge Position

The position of the surge is the longitudinal axis. Waves that interfere with the hovercraft either from

the front or back force the hovercraft to leap momentarily forward or backward. The position of this surge can be tested and observed with position and time curves. The reference position is shown for easy comparison with the actual position of the hovercraft. The surge position tracking results for both PID and fuzzy-PID controllers are shown in Figure 10 and Figure 11.

FIGURE 10. Trajectory tracking of surge position using PID controller

FIGURE 11. Trajectory tracking of surge position using FPID controller

Figure 10 shows the results of the hovercraft surge position when PID control is applied while Figure 11 shows the results of the hovercraft surge position when fuzzy-PID control is applied. A hovercraft with a PID controller takes 8 seconds to approach the full reference position while a hovercraft with a fuzzy-PID controller takes 1.5 seconds. This means, the response time taken by a hovercraft with a fuzzy-PID controller to achieve reference position accuracy is lower compared to a PID controller. The overshoot percentage on PID controllers is also higher compared to fuzzy-PID controllers. This gives the error between the actual hovercraft surge position and the reference surge position for a hovercraft is larger with a PID controller than a hovercraft with a fuzzy-PID controller.

Trajectory Tracking for Sway Position

The disturbance produces a motion that staggers the hovercraft and causes the hovercraft to tend to move to the left and right sides. The position of the sway is the transverse axis. This sway position can be tested and observed with position and time curves. The reference position is shown for easy comparison with the actual position of the hovercraft. The sway position tracking results for both the PID and fuzzy-PID controllers are shown in Figure 12 and Figure 13.

FIGURE 12. Trajectory tracking of sway position using PID controller

FIGURE 13. Trajectory tracking of sway position using FPID controller

Figure 12 shows the results of the hovercraft in sway position when PID control is applied while Figure 13 shows the results of the hovercraft surge position when fuzzy-PID control is applied. A hovercraft with a PID controller takes 5 seconds to approach the full reference position while a hovercraft with a fuzzy-PID controller takes 2 seconds. This means, the response time taken by a hovercraft with a fuzzy-PID controller to achieve reference position accuracy is lower compared to a PID controller. The overshoot percentage for the sway position for both controllers was lower compared to the surge position. The error between the actual sway position of the hovercraft and the reference sway position of the two controllers is low and only the response times of these two systems show a significant difference

Path Tracking

For path tracking control, the desired trajectory is based on easily accessible geometric parameters. In the simulation of this study, a circle of radius 1 was defined as trajectory tracking. The starting state of the hovercraft is set to the coordination of (0,0) with a directional angle of 0°. The hovercraft tracking performance for both controllers was observed and the simulation results are as shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15.

FIGURE 14. Path tracking using PID controller

FIGURE 15. Path tracking using FPID controller

The purple-lined reference path tracking is shown to facilitate comparison with the red-lined hovercraft's actual route tracking. Based on the simulation results, the controller system can track the full direction faster after adding fuzzy control function to the system. In addition to tracking directions faster, controller systems using fuzzy-PID also show lower tracking errors than PID controllers. The high response time to track the route gives a poor performance on the hovercraft. The hovercraft route tracking simulation using the target control model can also show this control tracks the desired route satisfactorily because the actual tracking almost matches the reference tracking.

Tracking Error Curve

For this tracking error curve, the horizontal axis is set for the time in seconds and the vertical axis is set for the error value. The tracking error curves of the two controller systems starting from the starting state have been combined in one figure shown in Figure 16.

FIGURE 16. Tracking error curve

Based on the results, the controller system can track the path completely and give a minimum error within 9 seconds after adding fuzzy control function on the system while on the system using PID controller only, the system takes 10 seconds to track the direction completely. In addition to tracking the direction faster, the controller system using fuzzy-PID also shows low overshoot, and steady-state error and high tracking accuracy.

DISCUSSION

By applying a fuzzy controller to tune the PID parameters, the hovercraft system can be improved. System overshoot on path tracking is lower compared to PID controllers. As expected, the target design methodology gives good performance on autonomous hovercrafts to track the desired route well. The actual path almost matches the

reference route. The path tracking error value achieved by the fuzzy-PID controller is smaller than that of the PID controller. Thus, the simulation results show that the autonomous hovercraft with the targeted control model can track the path and trajectory quicker and effectively with low tracking error and high accuracy than conventional PID control. The results indicate that the fuzzy-PID control-based autonomous hovercraft has many advantages in velocity control, system stability and anti-interference performance in route tracking and space.

CONCLUSION

The Design Optimization of fuzzy-PID Controller for Path Tracking of an Autonomous Hovercraft was proposed in this paper. Euler Lagrange approach is used to describe the dynamic and kinematic model of the autonomous hovercraft with external disturbances and common parameters of hovercraft. The proposed control model is fuzzy-PID which is a combination of PID controller and fuzzy controller that aims to improve the performance of classical PID controller for path tracking.

Simulations are conducted using MATLAB Simulink to test the proposed controller's effectiveness to drive the autonomous hovercraft along the desired path. The simulation also compares the performances of PID controller and fuzzy-PID controller. The results show that fuzzy-PID controller is suitable to be implemented in the autonomous hovercraft as it gives a better performance as compared to the classical PID controller. The proposed controller gives satisfactory results on the path tracking as the hovercraft can track the target trajectory more efficiently and faster with small tracking error dan good accuracy. The results also conclude that fuzz-PID controller is suitable to be implemented to an autonomous hovercraft surely has advantages in controlling velocities, improves stability and gives good performance in path tracking.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia and Elvira Systems for their support.

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